

Are Maxwell-Boltzmann Statistics A Special Solution of Tsallis Statistics?

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In a previous note (1), we tried to argue that the basic ideas of Maxwell-Boltzmann statistics follow from a deterministic conservation of energy equation for two body collisions, $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$. The basic idea is to introduce a product probability for (e_i,e_j) pairs with the same sum which is the same, meaning that one cannot distinguish between this product probability. This approach was then linked with constraints such that there exists a function $G= \text{Sum over } i \text{ } h(p(e_i)) p(e_i)$ with $dG=0 = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } c_i d(\text{constraint } i)$ where c_i is a constant, where $h(p(e_i))=-e_i/T$.

We argue here that $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ is a fundamental idea which may be used to develop a statistical framework, but that $p(e_1)p(e_2)=p(e_3)p(e_4)$ for $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$, is not the most general form. We suggest that a general form is: $\exp(h(p(e_i)))$ so that: $\exp(h(p(e_1))) \exp(h(p(e_2))) = \exp(h(p(e_3))) \exp(h(p(e_4)))$ for $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$. The MB case involves $h=\ln$ so that \exp and h essentially cancel, but more general cases are possible. A more general case should involve different a priori constraints than the MB one (because we argue that one may obtain the distribution directly from differentials of the constraints). We suggest, however, that one should have physical constraints.

Based on these ideas, we argue that the Tsallis framework is a more general one than the MB case, and that the MB result is a special solution of the more general Tsallis scheme.

The Importance of $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$

We argued in (1) that the entire MB statistical scheme follows from the deterministic conservation $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$. In particular, we suggested that one cannot distinguish between product probabilities for (e_1,e_2) and (e_3,e_4) (or any other (e_i,e_j) with the same sum, i.e.

$$p(e_1)p(e_2)=p(e_3)p(e_4) \quad ((1))$$

Then: $\ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ or $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$, the MB distribution ((2))

A different way of obtaining this result is to consider the two a priori constraints:

$$\text{Sum over } i \text{ } p(e_i)=1 \quad ((3a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave} \quad ((3b))$$

Writing: $G = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } p(e_i) h(p(e_i))$ with $h(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ one has:

$$dG=0 = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } c_i d(\text{constraint } i) \quad ((4))$$

$$h(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad \text{and} \quad p(e_i) dh/dp(e_i) = 1 = c_2 \quad ((5))$$

At first this may seem like a general approach, but we argue here that it is not. A more general approach, still based on the fundamental deterministic $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ is:

$$\exp(C h(p(e_1))) \exp(C h(p(e_2))) = \exp(C h(p(e_3))) \exp(C h(p(e_4))) \quad ((6)) \text{ for } e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$$

$h(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$. The MB case involves $h=\ln$ and is linked with the constraints ((5)), but we seek a more general solution for which $h(p(e_i))$ is not $\ln(p)$.

One may note, however, that ((6)) is still based on statistics linked with $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$. At this point, one has no idea what $h(p(e_i))$ should be, but may suggest that a different set of physical constraints than ((3)) are needed and that the MB case should arise as a special solution.

A More General Scheme

$p(e_i)$ is a probability which is a function of the input variable e_i (energy). This does not mean, however, that $p(e_i)$ is the probability for this energy to be present. In the simple MB case, this direct situation does exist, but physically more general schemes are possible, especially if there is a cycling feature. For example, one may not be able to associate $p(e_i)$ with the production or existence of e_i even if $p(e_i)$ is a function of e_i . As we have argued before, one may have $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ for a first cycle, but it may require q cycles before one may actually obtain e_i . In such a case, the extensive quantity e_i is linked with $p(e_i)$ power q (which is not normalized). A physical example is a seed of type i which is guaranteed to produce e_i if it produces if it germinates. The key then is for it to germinate and this takes q days. Thus, there may be q cycles in which the seed has a probability $p(e_i)$ to survive in each one. There is a re-setting for each cycle. (For example, $p(e_i)$ may be the probability that a seed is not eaten in a given day by a bird.) Thus, it seems physically reasonable to have the constraints:

$$\sum_i e_i p(e_i)^q = F \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_i p(e_i) = 1 \quad ((7))$$

One may note that for $q=1$, one obtains the MB case.

If one considers information lost to be linked with ((6)), this is the more general statistical idea. One may proceed to use the procedure ((4)) which is consistent with ((6)) because it uses $h(p(e_i))$. In other words, $h(p(e_i))=-e_i/T$ is introduced because of the general statistical information idea of ((6)). Then one has:

$$h(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad \text{and} \quad p(e_i)^q \frac{dh}{dp(e_i)} = 1 \quad ((8))$$

$$\text{If } q=1 \text{ is to yield the MB case, one has: } h(p(e_i)) = 1/(1-q) (1+ (1-q) p(e_i)^q) \quad ((9))$$

((9)) is linked with a more general scheme than the MB one, but both are based on the same starting point, i.e. $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ and the associated loss of information ((6)). One does not need to create the Tsallis distribution by arguing a priori that one seeks a power law tail, but rather that $p(e_i)^q$ arises physically in nature due to q cycles in which $p(e_i)$ is reset each time.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the Tsallis scheme is a more general one than the MB, and that the MB solution arises as a special case. We suggest that in general the basic statistics arise from the deterministic conservation law $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$. The key is that one wishes to have information lost linked with (e_1, e_2) pairs with the same sum, but the general way to do this is to use: $\exp(C h(p(e_1))) \exp(C h(p(e_2))) = \exp(C h(p(e_3))) \exp(C h(p(e_4)))$, where $h(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$. This we argue is the key idea for introducing $h(p(e_i))$. One may then link this idea with a set of constraints such that for $G = \sum_i h(p(e_i)) p(e_i)$, $dG=0 = \sum_i c_i d p(e_i)$ (constraints). $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ is completely general, but $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$ is not. We suggest that one may have the physical constraint $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)^q = F$, if there are q cycles in a problem which reset $p(e_i)$ for each cycle. In the case of $q=1$, one obtains the MB case. Thus, q arises physically and not through a desire to create a power law tail. This approach leads to the Tsallis distribution, which for $q=1$, becomes the MB, but we argue that the initial idea is the desire to associate a loss of information with the deterministic conservation law $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Determinism At the Root of Shannon's Entropy? (preprint, zenodo, 2025)